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Interaction between Open Source and Standardisation

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Module Objectives

After completing this module, you should be able to:

1. to understand the difference between standardisation and open source
2. to understand their interactions from ideation to diffusion
3. to identify their strengths and weaknesses.

About The Authors

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Mirko Boehm is a free and open source software contributor, community builder, licensing expert and researcher, with contributions to major open source projects like the KDE Desktop, the Open Invention Network, the Open Source Initiative and others. He has a PhD in innovation economics and is a visiting lecturer and researcher on free and open source software at the Technical University of Berlin. Mirko has a wide range of experience as an entrepreneur, corporate manager, software developer and German Air Force officer. He joined the Linux Foundation in June 2023 as senior director for community development for Linux Foundation Europe, where he focuses on driving engagement and collaboration between all European open source stakeholders. Mirko speaks English and German and lives in the Berlin area.

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Knut Blind studied economics, political science, and psychology at Freiburg University. During his studies, he spent one year at Brock University (Canada), where he was awarded a BA. Finally, he earned his Diploma in Economics and later his doctoral degree at Freiburg University. Between 1996 and 2010, he joined the Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research, Karlsruhe, Germany, as a senior researcher and, at last, as head of the Competence Center “Regulation and Innovation”. In April 2006, Knut Blind was appointed Professor of Innovation Economics at the Faculty of Economics and Management at the Berlin University of Technology. Between 2008 and 2016, he also held the endowed chair of standardization at the Rotterdam School of Management of Erasmus University. From April 2010 to September 2019, he was linked to the Fraunhofer Institute of Open Communication Systems in Berlin. Since October 2019, he has been head

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The interaction between the open source ecosystem and standardisation

1. Understanding the interaction between standard setting organisations and the open source ecosystem: An introduction

In the world of technology and innovation, two forces have played a pivotal role in shaping the landscape: standard setting organisations (SSOs) and open source communities. While distinct in their productive processes and outputs, the two ecosystems often intersect in ways that can either be collaborative or competitive. This tutorial introduces the key concepts elaborated in detail in the paper "Standard Setting Organizations and Open Source Communities: Partners or Competitors?" by Boehm and Eisape, which explores the complex relationship between these two influential groups.

What are standard setting organisations?

SSOs are formal bodies that develop, establish, and promote technical standards that ensure the interoperability, safety, and quality of products and services across industries. These standards are critical for ensuring that different technologies can work together seamlessly. For example, the standards set by organisations, like the International Organization for Standardization (ISO), the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) or the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), allow devices from different manufacturers to communicate effectively, which is essential in fields like telecommunications, manufacturing, and information technology.

What are open source communities?

Open source communities consist of participants or contributors who collaboratively create and maintain open source software, data, hardware designs, knowledge or other outputs. The source code of open source software is made freely available for anyone to view, modify, and distribute. Prominent examples of open source projects include the Linux operating system, the Apache web server, and the Python programming language. These communities thrive on collaboration and shared knowledge, with an emphasis on innovation and rapid development. The open source model has led to the creation of many widely-used technologies that are essential in various industries.

Partners and Competitors: The Relationship Between SSOs and open source communities

The relationship between SSOs and open source communities is complex and multifaceted. On the one hand, SSOs and open source communities can be seen as partners. Open source software often implement and promote standards set by SSOs, ensuring that the software adheres to widely accepted protocols and frameworks. This partnership can drive innovation, as open source communities rapidly develop and improve technologies that comply with these standards.

On the other hand, SSOs and open source communities can also be viewed as competitors. SSOs typically operate through a more formal, slower, and consensus-driven process, whereas open source communities often move quickly, driven by the collective efforts of their members. This difference in pace and methodology can sometimes lead to tensions, particularly when open source projects innovate in ways that diverge from established standards, or when SSOs perceive open source projects as bypassing the traditional standard-setting process.

In sum, open source communities and SSOs are partners and competitors at the same time, but for different aspects of technical standardisation. Both create complementary outputs, where SSOs focus on creating and approving technology specifications in working groups, while open source communities produce implementations that respond to specifications and technical requirements. Regarding the collaboration process, both offer alternative approaches. SSOs follow a specification-first approach, where the implementation of standard-conforming products is left to downstream manufacturers. In contrast, open source communities apply an implementation-first approach, where specifications follow if necessary after working code is available. Overall this means that the outputs of open source communities and SSOs complement each other, while their collaboration processes are competing alternatives.

Collaboration opportunities and inhibitors

The tension between these different approaches results in a number of key challenges to successful collaboration:

- **Methods of collaboration:** SSOs collaborate in a well-established and somewhat formalised manner that reflects their recognition by governments and adoption by small businesses to large enterprises. Open source communities often opt for radical transparency and open governance. This provides a crucial opportunity for finding more effective ways to collaborate. This might involve SSOs adopting more flexible processes that can keep pace with the rapid development cycles of open source projects, as well as open source communities engaging more in formal specification.
- **Governance and intellectual property frameworks:** Different understandings of governance models and approaches to IP rights can cause uncertainty about how to join and participate in development efforts.
- **Innovation versus standardisation:** Approved specifications provide stability, but also pose a barrier to the emergence of new technical approaches. Open source communities often push the boundaries of innovation by wild experimentation and early releases, which can sometimes lead to conflicts with broad compatibility and stability.

The theoretical framework of phased standardisation aims to bridge the gap between standards and open source development and to bridge these divides.

2. Phases of technical standardisation

To be able to explain the interaction between the open source ecosystem and standardisation, it is necessary to apply a broader understanding of standards development, since open source communities establish technical standards without starting from a formally adopted specification. The framework applied here begins with a need for standardisation, which is satisfied by applying a standardisation instrument until the resulting technical standard is adopted in the market. The work of SSOs is one standardisation instrument, that of open source communities another one, however other standardisation instruments like behavioural norms or guild customs can also be observed. SSOs and open source communities are the dominant standardisation instruments in digital markets.

Needs for standardisation

Standardisation serves specific societal and market purposes. From a societal perspective, standards are necessary to ensure product safety or to build markets for desired solutions, often resulting in a regulatory top-down push for standardisation. In markets, standards are beneficial to realise economies of scale or ensure interoperability, resulting in a bottom-up market pull for standardisation.

Standardisation needs have evolved significantly with the rise of open source communities and the increasing complexity of modern digital technologies. In the traditional model, the need for standardisation was primarily driven by the requirement for interoperability and safety across products from different manufacturers. SSOs addressed these needs by developing comprehensive standards that could be adopted across an industry, ensuring that products met specific performance and safety criteria. However, as technology has advanced, especially with the proliferation of software and digital services, the needs for standardisation have become more dynamic and immediate. Open source collaboration methods are one response to the need for fast and dynamic technology development and adoption.

Standardisation instruments

Standardisation instruments refer to the various tools, processes, and frameworks employed by SSOs, open source communities and other groups to develop, implement, and enforce technical standards. A standardisation instrument facilitates the transition from a need for standardisation to the adoption of the preferred solution in the market. In this context, SSOs provide a standardisation instrument, while open source communities provide another. They apply different processes, but aim to achieve similar goals.

SSOs traditionally use formal instruments such as technical committees, consensus-building processes, and the publication of official standards documents. These instruments are designed to create widely accepted standards that ensure consistency and compatibility across products and services globally.

Open source communities utilise more informal and flexible processes to achieve adoption. These include collaborative code repositories, community-driven governance, and iterative development processes where standards emerge organically from a competition of ideas. Open source standardisation instruments are often more

adaptive, allowing for rapid updates and real-time testing within the community.

Ideation phase

Ideation is triggered by needs for standardisation, where innovation begins with the generation of new ideas and the initial development of novel technologies. Traditionally, ideation was driven by corporate research and development as well as academic knowledge transfer or spin-offs. Today, open source communities play a critical role as well due to their collaborative and experimental nature. The “release early, release often” philosophy combined with a focus on “working code” lead to a competition of ideas, until candidates for wider adoption naturally emerge. The outcomes of the ideation phase set the groundwork for wide market adoption if the technology shows promise and gains traction. However, wider adoption will only be achieved once the ideation phase results in viable technology options for specification and implementation.

Specification phase

The specification phase of standards development is a critical stage in the process where the detailed technical requirements and guidelines for a new standard are defined and documented. Many technologies require detailed specifications to overcome barriers to adoption or ensure compliance with regulatory requirements. Specifications describe the requirements that products need to implement to be standards compliant. Technical requirements are derived from the standardisation needs and drafted into specification documents. Traditionally, SSO working groups collaborate on the authoring of specifications, stakeholder consultation, finalisation and approval. Today, approval by a recognized body is often omitted as technologies developed by less formalised stakeholder groups become widely adopted industry standards.

Implementation phase

The implementation phase is the stage where the technology is applied by businesses that create products that embody the standard and introduce them into practice across relevant industries, technologies, or systems. Implementation results in the availability of unfinished (e.g., software components) or finished products that embody the aspired technical solutions. This phase is crucial because it determines the impact of the technology on the industry and markets, and whether it achieves its intended goals of interoperability, safety, efficiency, or innovation. While traditionally implementation is based on the availability of approved specifications, it is the starting point for open source collaboration.

Adoption phase

Once products that satisfy the need for standardisation are available, markets will begin to adopt them. The success of a standardised technology relies heavily on sweeping penetration of the target markets. Digital technologies achieve wide market adoption through a combination of factors that include compelling value propositions, technological innovation, the creation of ecosystems that foster widespread use and regulatory compliance. Once widely adopted, technical standards deliver economies of scale and encourage competition of conforming products. While approved specifications are not required to achieve widespread adoption, it is difficult for regulators to reference technologies that are not formally specified. Hence, the response to a regulatory push for standardisation often requires the creation of formalised or, especially in the EU, harmonised¹ standards. The need for standardisation is fulfilled with the successful adoption of a corresponding technical solution. The standardisation process often starts a new iteration at this point as new requirements have emerged.

3. Methods of collaboration

The focus of collaboration is different between SSOs and open source communities.

Collaboration within SSOs involves a structured, consensus-driven process where representatives from various industries, companies, governments, and other stakeholders come together to develop and agree upon technical standards. These stakeholders participate in working groups, committees, and technical panels to discuss, draft, and refine standards that ensure interoperability, safety, and quality across products and services. The collaboration is formal, often requiring extensive negotiation and compromise to balance diverse interests, but it is crucial for creating widely accepted standards that facilitate global trade, innovation, and technological compatibility. The primary focus is on creating formally approved specifications.

¹ https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/european-standards/harmonised-standards_en (European Commission)

Open source collaboration is a decentralised and community-driven approach to software development where individuals and organisations contribute to and co-create software projects that are freely available to the public. Participants from diverse backgrounds—ranging from individual developers to large corporations—work together to write, review, and improve code, often through online development platforms. This collaborative process is transparent, with all code, discussions, and decisions openly accessible, fostering innovation, rapid iteration, and collective problem-solving. The primary focus is on implementing specific software solutions.

Consensus versus rough consensus

SSOs find consensus through a structured, iterative process that involves extensive discussion, negotiation, and compromise among diverse stakeholders. Representatives from various industries, companies, and interest groups participate in working groups and committees where they propose, debate, and revise standards. The process often includes multiple rounds of drafting, public comments, and reviews to address concerns and incorporate feedback. Consensus is typically achieved when there is broad, though not necessarily unanimous, agreement that the standard meets the needs of all parties involved. This method ensures that the final standard reflects a balanced approach, accommodating different perspectives while fulfilling the primary goals of interoperability, safety, and quality. In an open and decentralised development process, such a level of agreement is almost impossible to achieve. Instead, open source communities often aim for “rough consensus”. Rough consensus is a decision-making approach where agreement is reached *during* the ongoing implementation process not by unanimous vote but by general alignment and the absence of strong opposition within the community. Rough consensus values the collective input of contributors, allowing progress as long as the majority agrees and any dissenting opinions are addressed but not necessarily resolved completely. This flexible and pragmatic method enables open source projects to move forward efficiently, balancing diverse perspectives while avoiding the gridlock that can occur in more formal consensus processes.

Access to specifications

SSOs make standards available by publishing them through formal channels after they have been developed and approved. Once a standard is finalised, it is typically documented in a detailed technical format and made accessible to the public or specific industries. SSOs use their copyright over these materials to distribute them in print or through their official websites, where they can be purchased or, in some cases, freely downloaded. Additionally, SSOs might offer access to standards through partnerships with industry associations, academic institutions, libraries, or online platforms that aggregate technical standards. To ensure widespread use and compliance, SSOs often provide supplementary materials, such as implementation guidelines, certification programs, and educational resources.

Open source communities make source code and specifications available by freely distributing them on the internet, where the source code is openly accessible to anyone. The artefacts are distributed under an open source licence that allows anybody to use the work for any purpose. Additionally, open source communities often provide support through forums, mailing lists, and issue trackers, fostering a collaborative environment where users and developers can contribute to ongoing improvements and updates.

The introduction of open source licensing of code and specifications has changed expectations towards the availability of specifications, especially when they are referenced in any form in regulation. Stakeholders increasingly expect that specifications are generally available online, undermining the viability of the pay-for-access business models of some SSOs. This tension can limit widespread use and adoption of standards, especially in open source projects that prioritise free and open access to software and its underlying code. This poses challenges for integrating standards into open source projects, as the cost and restrictions of SSO standards can conflict with the open, collaborative ethos of open source communities, potentially hindering innovation and interoperability.

Licensing of implementations

In an open source development environment, development and implementation are the same process. Contributors collaborate by submitting changes and improvements to a joint implementation, which are integrated into the software released by that community. Since the software is available under an open source licence, everybody interested can use and redistribute it without the need to negotiate with the contributors or the community. Products that implement formal standards are usually made available after the standard is published. Access to the standard does not convey the rights to potential standards-essential patents. Product manufacturers need to acquire such licences separate from gaining access to the standard. SEP licences are necessary for making standards

conforming products available in the market, while access to the specification is required to ensure and certify conformance.

The overwhelming majority of successful open source projects strictly avoid incorporating functionality into their releases that requires the acquisition of separate patent licences. While there is no legal requirement for royalty free licensing of patents embodied in open source software, in practice it is a precondition for building a viable community of contributors and adopters.

4. Conclusion

The tension between how SSOs make standards available and how open source communities develop and distribute software arises from the differing approaches to accessibility and use. SSOs often charge for access to standards or impose restrictions on their distribution, which can limit widespread use and adoption, especially in open source projects that prioritise free and open access to software and its underlying code. In contrast, open source licensing promotes transparency, collaboration, and the unrestricted sharing of code. This difference creates challenges for integrating standards into open source projects, as the cost and restrictions of SSO standards can conflict with the open, collaborative ethos of open source communities, potentially hindering innovation and interoperability.

However, cooperation between these two groups has the potential to lead to mutual benefits. By working together, open source communities and SSOs can combine the agile, innovative nature of open source development with the stability and wide acceptance of formal standards. Through strategic partnerships, open source projects can incorporate standardised protocols and interfaces, enhancing interoperability and broadening adoption, while SSOs can tap into the creativity and rapid development cycles of open source communities. This synergy can lead to more robust and widely adopted technologies, bridging the gap between informal, community-driven innovation and formal, industry-wide standardisation.

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